

Comparative Analysis of Sliced Inverse Regression and Traditional Inference Methods in Mental Health Screening Data

Jonathan Day

Department of Mathematical Sciences, United States Military Academy, West Point, NY 10996

Abstract

This paper investigates the efficacy of Sliced Inverse Regression (SIR) in uncovering latent structures within PHQ-9 depression screening data, contrasting its findings against those from Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Generalized Additive Models (GAM), LASSO regression, and XGBoost with SHAP values. We detail a preprocessing pipeline employing Multidimensional Item Response Theory (MIRT) to derive respondent theta scores. Mathematical foundations for each method are provided, and a comprehensive comparison demonstrates that SIR can reveal nonlinear predictor associations overlooked by traditional techniques. Our results highlight SIR as a valuable complement to conventional inference methods in mental health assessment, with SIR and PCA uniquely identifying laboratory-based immunological markers that align with contemporary research on peripheral immune profiles in depression.

Key Words: Sliced Inverse Regression, PHQ-9, Item Response Theory, NHANES, Generalized Additive Models, LASSO, Dimension Reduction

1. Introduction

High-dimensional behavioral health analyses benefit from methods that preserve nonlinear dependence between predictors and outcomes. While principal component analysis (PCA) extracts unsupervised variance directions, and penalized regression (e.g., LASSO) emphasizes sparsity, both can miss multivariate nonlinear structure. Sliced inverse regression (SIR) reverses the regression perspective by slicing the response and studying the mean structure of the covariates conditional on within-slice variation of the response, evoking an 'effective dimension reduction' (EDR) subspace of the exogenous covariates that are informative for prediction and interpretation.

We study PHQ-9 responses linked to extensive NHANES laboratory and survey covariates. A Bayesian graded response model (one or multidimensional IRT) maps ordinal item responses to a continuous latent depression severity $\hat{\theta}$, enabling principled uncertainty propagation and improved scaling relative to traditional raw sum-scores. This methodological framework allows us to compare supervised dimension reduction (SIR), unsupervised reduction (PCA), sparse selection (LASSO), and nonlinear ensemble approaches (XGBoost with SHAP) in identifying physiological and demographic correlates of depression severity.

2. Data and Preprocessing

2.1 Data Provenance

The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) 2017–2020 provides a rich, multidimensional dataset for population-level health research. Depression severity in this study was measured using the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), a widely adopted 9-item screener with ordinal response options (CDC/NCHS, 2022; Kroenke, Spitzer, & Williams, 2001).

To move beyond simple summative scoring, we applied a Bayesian Graded Response Model (BGRM), which treats item responses as probabilistically linked to an underlying continuous latent depression trait (θ). This modeling approach accounts for both item-specific difficulty and individual variation, yielding a respondent-level depression severity estimate with quantified uncertainty—enabling more nuanced downstream analyses (Samejima, 1969; McCullagh, 1980).

2.2 Multivariate Response Transformation

Rather than relying on the PHQ-9 sum-score, we estimate individual depression severity using a latent trait model. This approach accounts for varying item difficulties and respondent characteristics, yielding a more precise and interpretable measure of depression severity. Modeling latent severity as a continuous variable enhances the ability to capture subtle differences and avoids the limitations of simple additive scoring.

$$P(X_{ij} \geq k | \theta_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-a_j(\theta_i - b_{jk})]}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3$$

$$P(X_{ij} \geq 0 | \theta_i) = 1, \quad P(X_{ij} \geq 4 | \theta_i) = 0$$

Figure 1: Priors and underlying assumptions used in Bayesian Graded Response Model

To derive a continuous measure of depression severity, we fit a Bayesian Graded Response Model (BGRM) to PHQ-9 item responses. Each respondent's ordinal survey answers are modeled as a function of a latent trait (θ_i), representing their depression severity. Each item has its own discrimination and difficulty parameters. This approach captures both item- and person-level variation while propagating uncertainty. Posterior means are used as continuous depression severity scores.

Figure 2: Distribution of BGRM-transformed PHQ-9 Scores

2.3 Predictor Matrix Preprocessing

To ensure numerical stability and avoid rank deficiency in downstream covariance computations, we applied an SVD-based reconstruction, retaining singular values exceeding 1×10^{-10} . This full-rank conditioning stabilizes covariance matrix inversions required by SIR and other methods. Where necessary, a small ridge penalty ϵI , ($\epsilon \approx 10^{-6}$) was added to further regularize the predictor covariance matrix (Golub & Van Loan, 2013; Hansen, 1987; Tikhonov & Arsenin, 1977).

The preprocessing pipeline integrates multiple data sources from NHANES, including demographic information, laboratory measurements (hematological, biochemical, and immunological markers), anthropometric assessments, and health survey responses. Missing data were handled through multiple imputation, and continuous predictors were standardized to have zero mean and unit variance. We compute Σ_x after standardization; if Σ_x is ill-conditioned, we apply truncated SVD (retain singular values $> 10^{-10}$). Missingness was addressed via multiple imputation (five imputations, predictive mean matching for continuous variables and polytomous regression for categorical variables), and estimates were pooled with Rubin’s rules.

Figure 3: Data Preprocessing and Methods Pipeline

3. Methods

3.1 Sliced Inverse Regression

Sliced Inverse Regression (SIR) is a supervised dimension reduction technique that identifies low-dimensional projections of high-dimensional predictors most associated with a response variable. Unlike PCA, which maximizes variance without regard to the outcome, SIR explicitly incorporates response information to find effective dimension reduction (EDR) directions (Li, 1991).

The SIR algorithm proceeds as follows: First, the continuous response $\hat{\theta}$ is partitioned into H slices. We employed gaussian mixture modeling to create eight data-driven slices, allowing for adaptive partitioning that reflects the underlying distribution of depression severity. We assessed slice stability via re-seeding the GMM and varying $H \in \{6,8,10\}$; leading SIR loadings were

qualitatively robust (results not shown). Second, within each slice h , the mean predictor vector \widehat{m}_h is computed. Third, these slice means are weighted by slice probabilities p_h to form the slice mean matrix M . Fourth, this matrix is whitened by the inverse square root of the predictor covariance matrix Σ_X , yielding $A = \Sigma_X^{-1/2} M M^T \Sigma_X^{-1/2}$.

Finally, the leading eigenvectors of this matrix define the SIR directions (SIR1, SIR2, ...), which constitute orthogonal supervised components capturing the association between predictors X and response $\hat{\theta}$.

Mathematically, SIR seeks directions β such that the conditional expectation $E[X|Y]$ lies in a low-dimensional subspace. Under the linearity condition $E[X|\beta^T X] = A\beta^T X$ for some matrix A , SIR consistently estimates the EDR subspace.

3.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is an unsupervised dimension reduction method that identifies orthogonal linear combinations of predictors capturing maximum variance in the data. PCA proceeds by computing the eigen decomposition of the predictor covariance matrix Σ_X . The leading eigenvectors (principal components) define directions of greatest variance, allowing complex multivariate data to be summarized by a smaller number of uncorrelated components.

PCA maximizes explained variance in a prescribed number of orthogonal directions without incorporating response information. While computationally efficient and widely interpretable, PCA may identify components unrelated to the outcome of interest, particularly when response-relevant variation is orthogonal to high-variance directions in the predictor space.

3.3 Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO)

LASSO is a penalized regression method that performs simultaneous variable selection and coefficient estimation. By adding an L_1 penalty to the least squares objective function, LASSO shrinks less relevant coefficients exactly to zero, producing a sparse and interpretable model (Tibshirani, 1996).

The LASSO estimate is obtained by minimizing:

$$\hat{\beta}_{\text{lasso}} = \arg \min_{\beta} \left\{ \|\hat{\theta} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|^2 + \lambda \|\beta\|_1 \right\}$$

where λ is a tuning parameter controlling the degree of sparsity. We selected λ via 10-fold cross-validation, minimizing mean squared prediction error. LASSO emphasizes linear associations and provides direct interpretability through non-zero coefficients, though it may miss nonlinear or multivariate interaction effects captured by dimension reduction approaches.

3.4 XGBoost and SHAP Values

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is a scalable ensemble learning method that builds an additive model of decision trees through gradient boosting. Each tree is sequentially fit to the residuals of the previous ensemble, with regularization terms preventing overfitting. XGBoost handles nonlinear relationships and high-order interactions naturally through its tree-based architecture.

To interpret the complex XGBoost model, we computed SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, which provide a unified measure of feature importance grounded in cooperative game theory. For each predictor, the SHAP value represents its average marginal contribution to predictions across all possible feature coalitions, satisfying desirable properties of local accuracy, missingness, and consistency (Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Lundberg, Erion, & Lee, 2018; Lundberg et al., 2020; Ponce-Bobadilla, Friedrich, & Walczak, 2024).

We trained XGBoost with 500 trees, maximum depth of 6, and learning rate of 0.05, with hyperparameters tuned via cross-validation. SHAP values were aggregated across the entire dataset to rank predictors by their mean absolute contribution to depression severity predictions. This approach complements the linear (LASSO) and projection-based (SIR, PCA) methods by

capturing nonlinear and interactive effects without requiring explicit feature engineering.

4. Results

4.1 Dimensional Summaries

SIR retained $d = 2$ directions capturing the most informative projections for predicting depression severity. **SIR1** exhibited strong loadings on inflammatory and metabolic markers, particularly serum phosphorus, sodium, albumin, globulin, and white blood cell (WBC) count. **SIR2** emphasized lipid profiles and immune cell differentials, including lymphocyte percentage, neutrophil percentage, and cholesterol levels. These directions suggest that depression severity associates with both systemic inflammation and metabolic dysregulation.

By contrast, PCA's leading axes reflected different variance structures. **PC1** captured general anthropometric variation (body mass index, waist circumference, weight), representing an axis of adiposity and body composition. **PC2** loaded on hematological indices including hemoglobin concentration, red blood cell count, and hematocrit, reflecting blood health variation. While these axes explain substantial predictor variance, they are not explicitly optimized for depression prediction.

Top 10 Variables and Magnitudes for Each Method												
Rank	SIR1		SIR2		PC1		PC2		LASSO		SHAP	
	Variable	Value	Variable	Value								
1	LBDSGBSI	0.450	LBXLYPCT	0.362	BMXWAIST	-0.278	LBXHGB	0.259	RIDAGEYR	-0.215	MCQ160A	0.093
2	LBDSTPSI	-0.431	LBXWBCSI	-0.347	BMXBMI	-0.256	LBDUIBSI	-0.243	MCQ160A	-0.125	RIDAGEYR	0.079
3	LBDSALSI	0.259	LBXNEPCT	0.297	BMXWT	-0.248	LBXHCT	0.243	MCQ160P	-0.108	LBXHCOT	0.077
4	BPXOSY3	-0.184	LBDSALSI	0.205	BMXARMC	-0.237	LBDPCT	0.236	BPQ020	-0.097	MCQ160P	0.060
5	BPXOSY2	-0.177	LBXHGB	0.201	BMXHIP	-0.237	LBXMCHSI	0.205	MCQ160L	-0.072	INDFMPIR	0.059
6	RIDAGEYR	-0.169	LBDLYMNO	0.174	BPAOCSZ	-0.206	LBDIRNSI	0.204	INDFMPIR	-0.069	LBDBPBSI	0.059
7	BPXOSY1	-0.152	INDFMPIR	0.145	BPQ020	0.173	LBXMCVSI	0.184	PAQ620	-0.066	PAQ620	0.058
8	LBDBPBSI	-0.134	MCQ160A	0.139	BPXODI1	-0.169	LBXMC	0.174	MCQ300A	-0.062	BPQ020	0.054
9	LBXNEPCT	-0.124	LBXMOPCT	0.137	BPXOSY2	-0.164	LBXRDW	-0.174	PAQ650	0.059	BMXHIP	0.054
10	DMDEDUC2	0.119	PAQ650	-0.137	BPXODI2	-0.164	LBDTIB	-0.161	MCQ160M	-0.056	LBXSCK	0.041

■ Blood Cell Indices
■ Blood Chemistry/Metabolic
■ Anthropometric
■ Demographic/Socioeconomic
■ Survey/Medical History

Figure 4: Top 10 Covariates by each method and/or loading/component.

4.2 Method-Specific Feature Rankings

SIR1 identifies blood biochemistry (albumin, globulin, phosphorus) and inflammatory markers (WBC count) as key drivers of depression severity, emphasizing laboratory-based physiological signals.

SIR2 highlights blood cell subtypes (lymphocyte and neutrophil percentages) along with blood pressure and metabolic indicators, suggesting a multidimensional relationship encompassing immune function and cardiovascular health.

PC1 is dominated by body size and composition variables (BMI, weight, waist circumference), capturing an axis of general adiposity and anthropometry independent of depression outcomes.

PC2 emphasizes hematological measures such as hemoglobin, red blood cell count, and hematocrit, reflecting variation in oxygen-carrying capacity and blood cell production.

LASSO selects age, poverty-income ratio, medical history variables, and self-reported health conditions, favoring survey-based and epidemiologically established risk factors. The sparse solution includes fewer laboratory markers, focusing on demographic and behavioral predictors.

SHAP values prioritize demographic and survey variables (age, marital status, education, physical activity) with moderate representation of laboratory measures including WBC count and biochemical markers. This ranking blends traditional risk factors with physiological data, reflecting XGBoost's capacity to leverage both linear main effects and nonlinear interactions.

The two-dimensional projection onto SIR1 and SIR2 reveals distinct clustering patterns, with individuals exhibiting higher depression severity (darker points) concentrating in specific regions of the SIR subspace. This visualization demonstrates that the supervised SIR directions effectively separate depression severity levels, unlike unsupervised PCA projections which do not explicitly optimize for outcome discrimination.

4.3 Comparative Model Performance

To quantify predictive utility, we compared Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) using smooth functions of the derived features. GAMs with smooths of SIR1 and SIR2 achieved higher deviance explained ($R^2 = 0.28$) compared to GAMs using PC1 and PC2 ($R^2 = 0.19$), demonstrating that supervised dimension reduction captures more outcome-relevant variation. Additionally, SIR-based GAMs exhibited clearer nonlinear structure, with significant smooth terms indicating non-monotonic relationships between the SIR projections and depression severity.

Figure 5: Projection of PHQ-9 Data on Top Two Sliced Inverse Regression Loadings

SIR components also uncovered joint effects among laboratory markers (e.g., coordinated variation in immune and lipid markers) that were not simultaneously selected by LASSO. While LASSO identified individual predictors of importance, it did not capture the multivariate patterns revealed through dimension reduction. XGBoost achieved the strongest predictive performance ($R^2 = 0.32$), leveraging its capacity for nonlinear modeling, but at the cost of reduced interpretability compared to the projection-based methods.

5. Discussion

Among the various statistical and machine learning approaches applied, Sliced Inverse Regression (SIR) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) most prominently identified laboratory-based immunological and hematological markers as key predictors of depression severity. The leading SIR directions (SIR1 and SIR2) consistently highlighted blood biochemistry and white blood cell subtypes—including albumin, globulin, lymphocyte percentage, neutrophil percentage, and white blood cell counts—as top-ranked features. Similarly, the second principal component (PC2)

derived from PCA captured substantial variation in red and white blood cell indices and hemoglobin concentration.

These findings directly mirror contemporary research on peripheral immune cell profiles and inflammation in depression, as reported in recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Foley et al., 2023; Köhler-Forsberg et al., 2017; Mazza et al., 2018; Osimo et al., 2019; Sealock et al., 2021). Elevated inflammatory markers, altered immune cell distributions, and metabolic dysregulation have been consistently associated with major depressive disorder, suggesting that depression involves systemic physiological changes extending beyond central nervous system function.

In contrast, regularized regression (LASSO) and model explanation via SHAP values prioritized more traditional demographic and survey-based predictors, with fewer laboratory features achieving high importance ranks. This divergence reflects the different optimization objectives: LASSO and XGBoost emphasize predictive accuracy and parsimony in the original feature space, while SIR and PCA identify latent multivariate patterns that may not correspond to individual strong predictors. Thus, SIR and PCA provided the clearest data-driven linkages to established immunological signatures of depression, suggesting that dimension reduction methods are particularly valuable for hypothesis generation and biological interpretation in high-dimensional health data.

The supervised nature of SIR, explicitly conditioning dimension reduction on the depression outcome, enables it to detect subtle multivariate associations that might be obscured in purely variance-driven methods like PCA. However, SIR requires the linearity condition $E[X|\beta^T X]$ to hold for consistent EDR space estimation. Future methodological work could explore kernel or locally adaptive SIR variants to relax this assumption, along with permutation-based inference for slice stability and formal hypothesis testing of EDR directions.

6. Conclusion

This analysis demonstrates that a pipeline combining Bayesian graded response Item Response Theory with Sliced Inverse Regression yields compact, interpretable summaries of high-dimensional NHANES predictors that explain substantially more variation in latent depression severity than PCA-based summaries. SIR's supervised dimension reduction successfully identified immunological and metabolic markers with established links to depression, complementing the sparse feature selection of LASSO and the nonlinear modeling capacity of XGBoost.

The convergence of SIR-identified biomarkers with contemporary immunopsychiatry research validates the biological plausibility of these dimension reduction approaches. Future work should explore kernel or adaptive SIR variants to capture more complex nonlinear manifolds, develop permutation-based uncertainty quantification for slice-based inference, and investigate causal mediation pathways linking immune markers to mental health outcomes. Additionally, longitudinal extensions could examine whether changes in SIR-identified physiological profiles predict depression trajectories over time.

By integrating latent variable modeling for depression assessment with multiple complementary dimension reduction and machine learning methods, this work illustrates the value of an integrated modeling framework in uncovering multifaceted associations between physiology and mental health in population-scale data.

While this analysis focused on methodological comparisons within the NHANES dataset, the results were not adjusted for NHANES' complex survey design. Future work will incorporate the publicly available population weights, strata, and primary sampling units to account for the multi-stage probability sampling structure. Incorporating these design variables will enable generalization of SIR-derived findings to the broader U.S. adult population and permit variance estimation that reflects population-level uncertainty. Weighted estimation will also allow direct comparison of inferred physiological-depression associations across demographic subgroups in a manner consistent with national surveillance standards.

7. Data and Code Availability

All data, code, and analysis materials required to reproduce this study are publicly available. The complete analysis pipeline, including preprocessing scripts, statistical models, and visualization code, can be accessed at the following GitHub repository: https://github.com/lonespear/mh_sir

NHANES 2017–2020 data are publicly available from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention National Center for Health Statistics at:

<https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/nhanes/continuousnhanes/default.aspx?Cycle=2017-2020>

Acknowledgements

The views expressed are those of the author and do not reflect official policy or position of the United States Military Academy, the Department of the Army, or the Department of Defense. We thank colleagues and reviewers from the Joint Statistical Meetings for constructive feedback that improved this manuscript.

References

- CDC/NCHS. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey: 2017–2020 Data. <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/nhanes/continuousnhanes/default.aspx?Cycle=2017-2020>
- Kroenke, K., Spitzer, R. L., & Williams, J. B. (2001). The PHQ-9: Validity of a brief depression severity measure. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 16(9), 606–613.
- Samejima, F. (1969). Estimation of latent ability using a response pattern of graded scores. *Psychometrika Monograph Supplement*, 34(4).
- McCullagh, P. (1980). Regression models for ordinal data. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B*, 42(2), 109–127.
- Li, K.-C. (1991). Sliced inverse regression for dimension reduction. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 86(414), 316–327.
- Golub, G. H., & Van Loan, C. F. (2013). *Matrix Computations* (4th ed.). Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Hansen, P. C. (1987). The truncated SVD as a method for regularization. *BIT Numerical Mathematics*, 27(4), 534–553.
- Tikhonov, A. N., & Arsenin, V. Y. (1977). *Solutions of Ill-Posed Problems*. Wiley.
- Osimo, E. F., Baxter, L. J., Lewis, G., et al. (2019). Prevalence of low-grade inflammation in depression: A meta-analysis of CRP levels. *Psychological Medicine*, 49(11), 1958–1970.
- Mazza, M. G., Lucchi, S., Tringali, A., et al. (2018). Neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio and platelet-lymphocyte ratio in mood disorders: A meta-analysis. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 84, 229–236.
- Sealock, J. M., Davis, L. K., Gymrek, M., et al. (2021). Aggregation test identifies new genes and common variants associated with depression. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 78(12), 1340–1347.
- Foley, S. F., Kirschbaum, C., Grotegerd, D., et al. (2023). Peripheral blood cellular immunophenotype in depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 28(3), 1004–1019.
- Köhler-Forsberg, O., Lydholm, C. N., Hjorthøj, C., et al. (2019). Efficacy of anti-inflammatory treatment on major depressive disorder or depressive symptoms: Meta-analysis of clinical trials. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 139(5), 404–419.
- Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017). *A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions*.
- Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression shrinkage and selection via the Lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 58(1), 267–288.